

Reduction of bundle sheath size boosts cyclic electron flow in *C₄ Setaria viridis* acclimated to low light

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Model Description

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Model description

Note S1. A model for light reactions: ATP and NADPH production rate

A sub model for light reactions estimating the rate of ATP and NADPH made available under a certain *PPFD* was modified from Bellasio (2019). Briefly, two electron transport chains are simulated (but for simplicity we report only one set of equations), one in M and one in BS cell, both accounting for the presence of NDH (governed by the parameter f_{NDH}), which is essential for C_4 photosynthesis (Ishikawa *et al.*, 2016, Yamori and Shikanai, 2016). The light absorbed at leaf level is partitioned between BS and M cells using a light absorption partitioning parameter ($AB \frac{BS}{M}$) following Bellasio and Lundgren (2016), which can be experimentally resolved. Each electron transport chain allows regulation of the proportion of CEF, through the parameter f_{Cyc} , but the total light absorbed by PSI and PSII is maintained constant. The model schematic is shown in Figure 2 in the main text. Let I_2 be the light absorbed by PSII, which takes the value of $I_{2,0}$ when the proportion of electron flow at PSI which follow CEF (f_{Cyc}) equals zero. $I_{2,0}$ can be expressed as (Yin *et al.*, 2004):

$$I_{2,0} = s I_{Inc\ BS, \text{ or } M}, \text{ where } I_{Inc\ M} = \frac{PPFD}{1+AB \frac{BS}{M}}, \text{ and } I_{Inc\ BS} = I_{Inc\ M} AB \frac{BS}{M} \quad S1a, S1b, S1c$$

When $f_{Cyc}=0$, the electron flow through PSI (J_1) will equal that through PSII (J_2), and therefore

$J_{1,0}=J_{2,0}$ (where the subscript '0' reminds of $f_{Cyc}=0$). It follows, from Yin *et al.* (2004):

$$I_{1,0} = \frac{I_{2,0} Y(II)_{LL}}{Y(I)_{LL}}, \quad S2$$

where I_1 is the light absorbed by PSI, which takes the value of $I_{1,0}$ when $f_{Cyc}=0$, $Y(II)_{LL}$ and $Y(I)_{LL}$ are the initial yield of PSII and PSI, respectively, extrapolated under zero *PPFD*.

When CEF is engaged, I_1 increases by a quantity χ , dependent on f_{Cyc} , expressed as (Yin *et al.*, 2004):

$$I_1 = (1 + \chi) I_{1,0}, \quad S3$$

where χ is:

$$\chi = \frac{f_{Cyc}}{1+f_{Cyc}+Y(II)_{LL}}. \quad S4$$

If the total light absorbed (I) is constant, I_2 will be (Yin *et al.*, 2004):

$$I_2 = \left(\frac{1}{Y(II)_{LL}} - \chi \right) I_2 \text{ } Y(II)_{LL}, \quad S5$$

The electron flow through PSII (J_2) is:

$$J_2 = I_2 Y(II), \quad S6$$

The electron flow through PSI (J_1) is (Yin *et al.*, 2004):

$$J_1 = \frac{J_2}{1-f_{Cyc}}, \quad S7$$

J_1 and J_2 are calculated from the yield of photosystem II [$Y(II)$], depending on *PPFD* (Eqn S12).

Electron transport processes generate a proton gradient across the thylakoid membrane, used for ATP generation. The total ATP production rate (J_{ATP}) is obtained by summing the translocated or generated protons [one proton per electron results from water oxidation, one from electron flow through the cytochromes, J_{Cyt} , two from the electron flow through the Q-cycle, J_Q (Yin *et al.*, 2004) and two from the electron flow through NDH, J_{NDH} (Kramer and Evans, 2011)], and dividing by h , the number of protons required by ATP synthase:

$$J_{ATP} = \frac{J_2 + J_{Cyt} + 2J_Q + 2J_{NDH}}{h}, \quad S8$$

where J_2 is the electron flow through PSII; $J_Q = f_Q J_1$; $J_{Cyt} = (1-f_Q) J_1$; $J_{NDH} = f_{Cyc} f_{NDH} J_1$; f_Q is the level of Q-cycle engagement; f_{NDH} is the fraction of f_{Cyc} flowing through NDH; and J_1 is the electron flow through PSI.

After passing through PSI, electrons are either cycled to plastoquinone, used by alternative sinks (these include all sinks that are not assimilatory dark reactions, such as O_2 and NO_3^-), or to reduce $NADP^+$ (this is just the NADPH used in assimilatory dark reactions). The total NADPH production can be expressed as:

$$J_{NADPH} = J_1 \frac{1-f_{Cyc}-f_{Pseudocyc}}{2}, \quad S9$$

where $f_{\text{Pseudocyc}}$ is the fraction of J_1 used by alternative electron sinks. These include nitrogen metabolism (chiefly reduction) as well as the glutathione–ascorbate cycle. The glutathione–ascorbate cycle is known to depend on O_2 concentration and the availability of PSI acceptors (Schreiber and Neubauer, 1990, Miyake and Yokota, 2000). Here, we describe $f_{\text{Pseudocyc}}$ by simplifying from Bellasio (2018) as:

$$f_{\text{Pseudocyc}} = f_{\text{Pseudocyc NR}} + 4 \times 10^{-7} O_M. \quad \text{S10}$$

In this study we assumed $f_{\text{Pseudocyc NR}}$ to be small (see Parameterisation). $Y(II)$ was calculated as:

$$Y(II)_{\text{MOD}} = Y(II)_0 f(\text{PPFD}) f(C_M). \quad \text{S11}$$

The rationale of Eqn S11 is that $Y(II)$ has a maximum operational value, $Y(II)_0$, and is quenched by two distinct factors: 1) reaching the maximum capacity for electron transport; 2) a feedback from dark reaction linked to the availability of CO_2 as a substrate. These are captured by the functions $f(\text{PPFD})$ and $f(C_M)$, which we describe as two non-rectangular hyperbolic functions of PPFD and C_M :

$$f(\text{PPFD}) = 1 - \frac{\alpha_V \text{PPFD} + V_{0V} - \sqrt{(\alpha_V \text{PPFD} + V_{0V})^2 - 4\alpha_V \text{PPFD} \theta_V V_{0V}}}{2 \theta_V}, \quad \text{S12}$$

and

$$f(C_M) = \frac{\alpha_C C_M + V_{0C} - \sqrt{(\alpha_C C_M + V_{0C})^2 - 4\alpha_C C_M \theta_C V_{0C}}}{2 \theta_C}, \quad \text{S13}$$

where V_0 is the maximum value of the function, α scales the slope of the function and θ the curvature and are all fitted empirically (Table 2).

Note S2. Dark reactions and metabolite diffusion

A steady state model of C₄ photosynthetic carbon metabolism, including key reactions involved in the reductive pentose phosphate cycle (RPP), photorespiration pathway and carbohydrate synthesis, was newly developed. The biochemical flows are calculated through a set of stoichiometric constraints based on Bellasio (2017). Here we derived a novel set of equations that allow to explicitly calculate key reaction rates from ATP and NADPH production rates supplied by light reactions in M and in BS cells ($J_{ATP M}$, $J_{NADPH M}$, $J_{ATP BS}$, and $J_{NADPH BS}$ respectively, see above).

Based on Eqn S18 in Bellasio (2017), under the assumption of steady state, and assuming a full C₄ cycle, meaning that the strength of the C₂ cycle is zero, see Bellasio (2017), we can write:

$$J_{NADPH BS} = PR_{BS} + \frac{1}{2}V_O, \quad S14$$

where V_O , the Rubisco rate of carboxylation was calculated as:

$$V_O = V_C 2\gamma^* \frac{O_{BS}}{C_{BS}}, \quad S15$$

where γ^* is half the reciprocal Rubisco specificity, O_{BS} and C_{BS} are the O₂ and CO₂ concentration in BS cells, respectively (Farquhar *et al.*, 1980), and V_C , the rubisco rate of carboxylation was solved from Eqn S8 in Bellasio (2017) as:

$$V_C = \frac{J_{NADPH} + \frac{1}{3}R_{LIGHT}}{2 + 4\gamma^* \frac{O_{BS}}{C_{BS}}}, \quad S16$$

and, finally O_{BS} is calculated using the supply function of BS cells together with the actual rate of linear electron flow in BS cells derived above as:

$$O_{BS} = O_M + \frac{\frac{1}{4} J_{2BS}}{0.047 g_{BS}}, \quad S17$$

where $\frac{1}{4}$ states that four electrons flowing linearly through PSII in BS cells (J_{2BS}) are required to evolve one O₂, and 0.047 scales O₂ to CO₂ BS conductances and solubilities after Berry and Farquhar (1978).

Similarly, based on Eqn S24 in Bellasio (2017), under the assumption of steady state, and assuming a full C₄ cycle, *i.e.* the strength of the C₂ cycle is zero, and Rubisco is exclusively expressed in the BS, see Bellasio (2017), we can write:

$$J_{NADPH\ M} = PR_M + MDH_M. \quad S18$$

The total rate of PGA reduction [Eqn S4 in Bellasio (2017)] is:

$$PR_{TOT} = PR_M + PR_{BS} = 2V_C + \frac{3}{2}V_O - \frac{1}{3}R_{LIGHT}, \quad S19$$

We define as $\varepsilon J_{ATP\ BS}$ the ATP in BS cells that can be consumed for the regeneration of PEP by PEPCK and PPDK. Solving from Eqn S15 in Bellasio (2017) assuming a full C₄ cycle (see above):

$$\varepsilon J_{ATP\ BS} = J_{ATP\ BS} - PR_{BS} - V_C - 2V_O - \frac{1}{2}f_{CS} CS_{TOT}, \quad S20$$

where f_{CS} is the BS fraction of carbohydrate synthesis (CS), relative to the total rate of CS (CS_{TOT}), which we solve from Eqn S7 in Bellasio (2017) as:

$$CS_{TOT} = \frac{1}{3}V_C - \frac{1}{6}V_O - \frac{1}{3}R_{LIGHT}. \quad S21$$

The maximum rate at which PEPCK can operate equals $\varepsilon J_{ATP\ BS}$, since this would involve PEPCK consuming all ATP available for PEP regeneration in BS cells. The actual rate of PEPCK will be a fraction of $\varepsilon J_{ATP\ BS}$, which may vary between 0 and 1, that we call f_{PEPCK} :

$$PEPCK = f_{PEPCK} \varepsilon J_{ATP\ BS}. \quad S22$$

And, by definition, the complement $(1-f_{PEPCK})$ will be used by PPDK, operating at a rate of:

$$PPDK_{BS} = \frac{(1-f_{PEPCK})}{2} \varepsilon J_{ATP\ BS}, \quad S23$$

where 2 accounts for the ATP required by each PPDK cycle.

The rate of PPDK in M cells can be solved by combining Eqn S17 in Bellasio (2017) with Eqn S18 and S19 as:

$$PPDK_M = \frac{1}{2}J_{ATP_M} - \frac{1}{4}(1 - f_{CS})CS_{TOT} - V_C \left(1 + 2\gamma * \frac{O_{BS}}{C_{BS}}\right) + \frac{1}{6}R_{LIGHT} + \frac{1}{2}J_{NADP_{BS}} + \frac{1}{2}MDH_M. \quad S24$$

Assuming that all PEP produced by PEPC is either hydrolysed or used by PEPC, the rate of PEP carboxylation, V_P , can be written as:

$$V_P = PPDK_M + PPDK_{BS} + PEPC(1 - f_{PH}), \quad S25$$

where f_{PH} defines the fraction of PEP that is hydrolysed in BS cells, kept at zero in this study. The maximum rate of MDH in M cells can be derived from Eqn S19 in Bellasio (2017) as:

$$MDH_{M_{MAX}} = PPDK_M + PPDK_{BS}. \quad S26$$

The actual rate of MDH in M cells will be a fraction of the maximum possible activity that we call f_{MDH} :

$$MDH_M = f_{MDH} MDH_{M_{MAX}}. \quad S27$$

Finally, the supply function of CO_2 in BS cells can be written as (Berry and Farquhar, 1978):

$$C_{BS} = C_M + \frac{V_P + R_{LIGHT_{BS}} - V_C + \frac{1}{2}V_O}{g_{BS}}, \quad S28$$

where R_{LIGHT} is calculated as a fraction f_{RLIGHT} of R_{LIGHT} , C_M and C_{BS} are the CO_2 concentration in M and BS cells respectively. Eqn S14–S28 were solved for MDH_M , V_P , C_{BS} , PR_{BS} , $PEPC$, as reported in Sheet 3 of the workbook provided in Supporting Information.

Note S3. Balancing NADPH demand in BS cells

Transamination rate (T) is calculated as the fraction of OAA not reacted by MDH in M cells:

$$T = V_P - MDH_M. \quad S29$$

The rate of malate dehydrogenase in BS cells (MDH_{BS}) is:

$$MDH_{BS} = T - PEPCCK. \quad S30$$

The malic enzyme (ME) activity in BS cells is:

$$ME = MDH_M + MDH_{BS}. \quad S31$$

Note S4. Metabolite Fluxes between M and BS cells, and amino-group balancing

Sharing biochemical work between BS and M cells results in metabolite traffic. The model calculates the fluxes of MAL, PEP, PYR, ASP, ALA, PGA, DHAP, GLY, SER, as well as unbound CO₂ across the M–BS interface (Figure 2, main text). The fluxes between M and BS cells can be calculated either by M or BS mass balance, the simpler of the two equivalent alternatives is described. Fluxes are considered positive when occurring in the direction of the arrow in Figure 2, and vice versa.

The flux of DHAP from M to BS cells is calculated from DHAP mass balance in M cells as:

$$DHAP_{M \rightarrow BS} = PR_M - CS_M - DHAP_{RPPM}. \quad S32$$

The flux of PGA from BS to M cells is calculated from PGA mass balance in BS cells as:

$$PGA_{BS \rightarrow M} = 2V_{CBS} + 1.5V_{OBS} - PR_{BS}. \quad S33$$

The MAL produced by MDH in the M diffuses to BS cells, and the flux is:

$$MAL_{M \rightarrow BS} = MDH_M. \quad S34$$

Because no PEP is consumed in BS cells and the sources of PEP in BS cells are PEPCK (but a fraction f_{PH} is hydrolysed) and PPK, the flux of PEP from BS to M cells is:

$$PEP_{BS \rightarrow M} = PEPCK(1 - f_{PH}) + PPK_{BS}. \quad S35$$

The ASP diffusing to BS cells results from OAA transamination (Eqn S29) is:

$$ASP_{M \rightarrow BS} = T. \quad S36$$

In this model, the fraction of GLY decarboxylated in BS cells is entirely produced therein and, therefore, the GLY flux from M to BS cells is zero:

$$GLY_{M \rightarrow BS} = GDC_{BS} - V_{OBS} = 0. \quad S37$$

For the same reason:

$$SER_{BS \rightarrow M} = R = \frac{1}{2} GLY_{M \rightarrow BS} = 0. \quad S38$$

Glutamate and α KG do not diffuse directly between M and BS cells, but exchange amino-groups with ALA and PYR (Pick *et al.*, 2011, Mallmann *et al.*, 2014). The flux of ALA from BS to M cells corresponds to the fluxes of amino-groups imported in BS cells through (i.e. transamination rate, T) plus the surplus flux of amino groups deriving from GLY decarboxylation:

$$ALA_{BS \rightarrow M} = T + R. \quad S39$$

The flux of PYR from BS to M cells balances the activity of ME (producing PYR in BS), T (consuming PYR in BS cells), the flux of PYR required to rebalance the amino-groups in the C_2 shuttle, the activity of PPDK (consuming PYR in BS cells) and PEP hydrolysis (producing PYR in BS cells):

$$PYR_{BS \rightarrow M} = ME - T + R - PPDK_{BS} + PEPCK f_{PH}. \quad S40$$

Finally, the flux of CO_2 diffusing out of BS cells, the leakage rate (L) can be calculated by balancing all CO_2 fluxes in and out of BS cells as:

$$L_{BS \rightarrow M} = ME + PEPCK + R_{LIGHT\ BS} + \frac{1}{2} GDC_{BS} - V_{C\ BS}. \quad S41$$

Several ratios are calculated in the Excel workbook, including leakiness ($\phi=L/V_P$) and the ATP cost of gross assimilation (ATP/GA), but these are self-explanatory. Solutions are included in the workbook.

Figure S1. Schematic of the light reactions model. Light is shown in solid grey, electron fluxes in black, protein complexes are drawn as boxes, and proton delivery to the lumen is depicted by outlined arrows. I is the total light absorbed by two photosystems, and is a fraction of the light incident on the leaf ($PPFD$). I may be absorbed by PSI (I_1) or PSII (I_2). Electrons flowing through PSII (J_2) reach the plastoquinone and plastoquinol pool (PQ and PQH₂) simultaneously taking up protons from the stroma. Electrons flow to the Cytochrome b_6f where they may undergo the Q-cycle, which results the translocation of one additional proton (shown in grey), eventually reaching PSI through plastocyanin (not shown). Here, electrons may be cycled back through cyclic electron flow (CEF) to PQ, be used for alternative sinks (these include O₂ and NO₃⁻ in this model), or be used by photosynthetic dark reactions. CEF can follow two different paths, via PGR5 or through NDH which translocases two additional protons across the thylakoid membrane.

Figure S2. Spectra of growth light, measured in the cabinets at canopy height in HL conditions (purple) and LL conditions (green), normalised at 380 nm and at the maximum peak height.

Figure S3. Responses to *PPFD* of the fitted fraction of CEF relative to total electron flow through Photosystem I (f_{Cyc}) in the M (thin black lines) or the BS (thick grey lines) of HL plants (solid) or LL plants (dashed).

Table S1. C₄ photosynthesis parameters obtained from curve fitting of gas exchange responses of *S. viridis* grown at high light (HL) or low light (LL). We analysed the gas exchange data with the protocol and workbook of Bellasio *et al.* (2016a). To derive BS conductance we used the model of von Caemmerer (2000) with the procedure described in Yin *et al.* (2011), after Bellasio and Griffiths (2014b). The fitted value of respiration in the light derived concurrently under ambient and low O₂; the fraction of O₂ evolution in BS cells was assumed 0.05; M conductance was 1.5 for HL plants and 1.2 for LL plants derived by adjusting the data of Ubierna *et al.* (2018) for S_m (Table S1); the ATP required for gross assimilation was assumed 5.4 (Bellasio and Griffiths, 2014a); γ* was 0.000311 (Boyd *et al.*, 2015); x was 0.4 (von Caemmerer, 2000). K_C was 947 μbar; K_O was 289000 μbar, both from (Boyd *et al.*, 2015); V_CMAX and V_PMAX were set at the measured values *in vitro* [V_CMAX is 61 and 73 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹ for HL and LL respectively; V_PMAX is 182 and 158 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹ for HL and LL respectively], O_M was assumed equal to ambient, 210000 μbar. n = 3 biological replicates, p-values in bold indicate statistically significant difference between two light regimes (P < 0.05).

O ₂	Output	Unit	Description	HL		LL		p-value
				Mean	SE	Mean	SE	
21 %	R _{LIGHT} ^{1,a}	μmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Respiration in the light	1.93	0.23	1.18	0.03	0.03
2 %	R _{LIGHT} ^{1,a}	μmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Respiration in the light	1.70	0.29	1.43	0.02	0.25
21 %	Y(II) _{LL} ^{2,a}	dimensionless	Initial yield of PSII extrapolated to PPFD=0	0.73	0.003	0.70	0.01	0.04
2 %	Y(II) _{LL} ^{2,a}	dimensionless	Initial yield of PSII extrapolated to PPFD=0	0.64	0.04	0.69	0.001	0.18
21 %	LCP ^{1,b}	μmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Light compensation point, i.e. PPFD when A=0	37.1	4.15	22.32	0.67	0.02
21 %	GA _{SAT} ^{1,b}	μmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Light-saturated GA, under the CO ₂ concentration of light-curves	459	8.5	421	29	0.18
21 %	Y(CO ₂) _{LL} ^{3,b}	CO ₂ /quanta	Quantum yield for CO ₂ fixation, i.e. quanta required for each CO ₂ assimilated, extrapolated to PPFD=0; also known as Φ _{CO2LL} .	0.053	0.001	0.053	0.002	0.41
21 %	PPFD ₅₀ ^{1,b}	μmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	PPFD that half saturates GA	37.3	0.50	35.8	1.4	0.24
21 %	m ^{2,b}	dimensionless	Curvature of the non-rectangular hyperbola describing the PPFD dependence of GA	0.70	0.04	0.75	0.02	0.19
2 %	LCP ^{1,b}	μmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Light compensation point	34.2	4.7	25.8	0.37	0.11
2 %	GA _{SAT} ^{1,b}	μmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Light-saturated GA	32.1	2.1	36.4	1.0	0.10
2 %	Y(CO ₂) _{LL} ^{3,b}	CO ₂ /quanta	Quantum yield for CO ₂ fixation	0.049	0.003	0.056	0.000	0.06
2 %	PPFD ₅₀ ^{1,b}	μmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	PPFD that half saturates GA	370	32	407	20	0.24
2 %	m ^{2,b}	dimensionless	Curvature of the hyperbola	0.87	0.04	0.75	0.02	0.04
21 %	CE ^{4,b}	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Carboxylation efficiency, i.e. initial slope of the A/C _i curve	0.68	0.03	0.70	0.02	0.36
21 %	A _{SAT} ^{1,b}	μmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	CO ₂ -saturated A, under the PPFD of A/C _i curves	28.0	0.32	28.1	0.27	0.44
21 %	ω ^{2,b}	dimensionless	Curvature of the non-rectangular hyperbola describing the C _i dependence of A	0.84	0.01	0.91	0.01	0.01
21 %	Γ ^{1,b}	μmol mol ⁻¹	C _i -A compensation point, i.e. C _i at which A=0	2.3	0.2	3.4	0.2	0.01
2 %	CE ^{4,b}	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Carboxylation efficiency	0.75	0.01	0.62	0.01	0.00
2 %	A _{SAT} ^{1,b}	μmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	CO ₂ -saturated A	29.9	0.56	28.5	0.40	0.09
2 %	ω ^{2,b}	dimensionless	Curvature of the hyperbola	0.72	0.09	0.92	0.01	0.07
2 %	Γ ^{4,b}	μmol mol ⁻¹	C _i -A compensation point	2.6	0.2	3.1	0.3	0.18
2 %	s' ^{5,a}	ATP / Quanta	Combined conversion efficiency of incident light into ATP (Yin <i>et al.</i> , 2011)	0.222	0.01	0.243	0.002	0.11
21 %	J _{ATPSAT} ^{1,c}	μmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Light-saturated ATP production rate	219	26	194	11	0.25
21 %	θ ^{2,c}	dimensionless	Curvature of the non-rectangular hyperbola describing the PPFD dependence of J _{ATP}	0.67	0.1	0.71	0.05	0.38
21 %	PPFD ₅₀ ^{1,c}	μmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	PPFD which half saturates J _{ATP}	553	95	441	42	0.21
21%	g _{BS} ^{4,d}	mol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	BS conductance to CO ₂ diffusion	0.0018	0.0002	0.0012	0.0001	0.02
21 % and 2 %	V _P MAX ^{1,e}	μmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Maximum PEPC carboxylation rate	163	12	164	7.4	0.48

Method: ^a linear fitting of gas exchange and fluorescence (Yin *et al.*, 2011) following Bellasio *et al.* (2016a); ^b Fitted non-rectangular hyperbola (Bellasio *et al.*, 2016b); ^c non-linear calibration of Bellasio and Griffiths (2014b); ^d concurrent fitting of A/C_i and light curves under light limited conditions using non-linear estimates of J_{ATP} using the model of von Caemmerer (2000), following Bellasio and Griffiths (2014b) and Bellasio *et al.* (2016a); ^e concurrent fitting of 2 % and 21 % O₂ using the model of von Caemmerer and Furbank (1999), following Bellasio *et al.* (2016a). Units: ¹ μmol m⁻² s⁻¹; ² Dimensionless; ³ CO₂/quanta; ⁴ mol m⁻² s⁻¹

Table S2. C₄ photosynthesis model sensitivity analysis.

The analysis of model relative sensitivity (elasticity) quantifies the response of one of the model outputs to the variation of a given input, and is generally calculated as the relative change in an output ($\partial o/o$) divided by the relative change in the input ($\partial i/i$). Analysing the sensitivity of every output to every input would require studying circa 3000 relationships, at each level of inputs. Thus, for simplicity we analyse the output A for two biochemical subtypes in ordinary conditions (Table 2) and when $PPFD$ is set to $1500 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. The model is highly sensitive to the parameters defining light interception (s) and photochemical yield ($Y(II)_{LL}$), and the characteristics of quenching in response to $PPFD$ (α_v) and, to a lower extent, quenching in response to C_M (α_c). Other quantities defining light reactions are also influential (h, f_Q, f_{CycBS}). Regarding the parameters not associated with light reactions, the model is sensitive to R_{LIGHT} , γ^* and f_{PH} . Sensitivity was calculated as relative change in A ($\partial A/A$) divided by the relative change in the parameter ($\partial p/p$) for NADP-ME, and NAD-ME. Other inputs were set at levels listed in Table 1, $PPFD$ was $1500 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.

Input	Relative Sensitivity	
	NADP-ME $f_{PEPCK} 0.5$	NAD-ME $f_{PEPCK} 0.5$
g_{BS}	-0.022	-0.014
Y^*	-0.039	-0.029
R_{LIGHT}	-0.039	-0.042
$AB\ BS/M$	0.044	0.067
$Y(II)_{LL}$	0.96	0.9
s	1.1	1.1
$f_{PSEUDO\ NR\ M}$	-0.0057	-0.01
$f_{PSEUDO\ NR\ BS}$	-0.009	-0.0099
f_Q	0.12	0.05
h	-0.34	-0.14
$Y(I)_{LL}$	0	0
$f_{NDH\ M}$	0	0.01
f_{NDHBS}	0.034	0.0077
$f_{Cyc\ M}$	-0.0002	0.0017
$f_{Cyc\ BS}$	-0.36	-0.83
α_c	0.07	0.07
θ_c	0	0
α_v	-0.92	-0.89
θ_v	-0.75	-0.7
f_{PH}	-0.041	-0.018
f_{RLIGHT}	0.0027	0.0012
f_{CS}	0.0022	0.0004

Supporting References

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